

ZAMBAYANIHAN: ROLES OF ZAMBALES' YOUTH VOLUNTEER ORGANIZATIONS IN NATION BUILDING

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Article history:	Abstract:
<p>Received: April 10th 2021 Accepted: April 22th 2021 Published: May 25th 2021</p>	<p>This descriptive survey research evaluated the roles of the Zambales' Youth Volunteer Organizations, particularly as to leadership, crisis response, environmental protection, indigenous people, and education in the province. Most of the youth volunteer organizations were situated at Iba, Zambales. Findings revealed that most of the organizations' objectives affirmed that they imparted the various communities with essential knowledge and developed basic life skills by providing programs and training to build a better community and environment. The data gathered reflected that the role of volunteers in promoting leadership was Excellent through inspiring youth to become responsible in helping others wherein the inculcation of hard work is important to achieve goals. They also marked Excellent in promoting crisis response as they encourage people to characterize the spirit of Bayanihan, especially in times of adversity. Moreover, they were categorized as Excellent in Environmental protection as they encourage people to take part in coastal clean-up drive to protect marine life with the participation of other Non-Government Organizations. Furthermore, it was revealed that they were also Excellent in helping Indigenous People, for they conduct gift-giving/relief operations that will instill the value of sharing to the community. As for education, it was confirmed that they were Excellent through helping people to recognize the value of individuality by knowing how to socialize with others to achieve common goals in life. Lastly, it was revealed that the common best practice of the youth volunteer organizations is to be selfless by initiating various programs that raise awareness in protecting the environment and natural resources as well as the promotion of the Bayanihan spirit through collaboration with other agencies and linkages to achieve their specific goals, the betterment of the community.</p>

Keywords: Bayanihan, youth volunteer organizations, roles, non-government organizations

INTRODUCTION

Volunteerism is an attribute or character that most people possess for the simple reason that human society and community growth need it (Nurfarahin et al., 2018). According to Rehberg (2005), it is a fundamentally social activity that contributes to the unity, stability, and enjoyment of our community and living conditions. Globally, volunteerism has been regarded as a significant achievement of the state, as it almost always strengthens the social care system and assists the most vulnerable members of society (Tran, 2016).

The *Bayanihan* spirit is one of the prominent values reflected in Filipino society. Caring and helping others has always been a norm as it is one of the essential values passed down by the forefathers. Each one contributes based on the things that they can give and do to help lessen the burden of their fellow citizens. There are a lot of possible ways to help others as everyone is unique and distinctly skillful in their own ways. According to Brennan (2007), volunteers are at the heart of effective community building and are frequently the driving force behind successful efforts.

Moreover, few people decide to help others alone, but some of them form organizations with the same goal of helping and inspiring needy people. According to Gage III and Thapa (2011), the low involvement is due to the lack of a

systematic and consistent volunteer sector, which causes youth to lack awareness and exposure to engage in volunteer activities. Since teamwork is very important to make the goals easy in the earliest possible time, more people means more hands combined to attain the shared goals of helping people in adversity. They formed organizations that created specific objectives that they focused on so they can maximize their resources to attain their goals.

In Zambales, there are a lot of Youth Volunteer Organizations (YVOs) that have helped the needy Zambaleños to deal either with calamities or to have a better way of living through various assistance programs and seminars. The various YVOs focused on five areas, namely leadership, crisis response, environment, Indigenous People, and education. Each YVOs focused on various areas, and there are circumstances that, in one way or another, they have helped in other areas as well, depending on the given situation.

This study aimed to evaluate the roles of the YVOs in terms of leadership, crisis response, environmental protection, Indigenous people, and education in Zambales as it is integral in the development of needy people or communities. This would deepen the understanding of the respective goals and extent of help provided by YVOs in the betterment of the province in general.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study evaluated the roles of the YVOs in the development of the community depending on their focused area. The research sought to identify the location of the YVO's office, the specific organization's goals, the roles of the YVOs in terms of leadership, crisis response, environmental protection, Indigenous people and education, and the YVO's best practice.

Quantitative methods emphasize objective measurements and the statistical, mathematical, or numerical analysis of data collected through polls, questionnaires, surveys, or by manipulating pre-existing statistical data using computational techniques. Quantitative research focuses on gathering numerical data and generalizing it across people or explaining a particular phenomenon (Babbie, 2010).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows the location of the YVOs.

Figure 1. Location of the YVOs

The results revealed that most of the YVOs were located at Iba, the capital of Zambales. The people from the capital have easy access to the various public offices that offer a variety of services from the government.

Table 1 presents the goals and objectives of Zambales' YVOs.

Table 1. Goals and Objectives of Zambales' YVOs.

Respondents	Goals and Objectives
R1	Service Above Self - to help the most vulnerable person and community and to restore humanity.
R2	A non-profit socio civic program which aims to make the dreams of the community comes true, in terms of education and livelihood.
R3	Non-Government Organization
R4	To be a catalyst of the Sustainable Development Goals.
R5	Aspires to create good impact in environment and the community.
R6	To serve humanity.
R7	A movement focusing in developing an individual to be a responsive leader in building our nation, and believes that through our collective strength and resources, we can prepare and create an upright environment for next generation.
R8	To insulate the youth from radicalization efforts of both the communist movement and Islamic terrorists. It is also a strategic response towards addressing the threat of illegal drugs on the Philippine youth. Through the PNP Police Community Relations platform, it seeks to empower both youth and student sectors to become resilient to radical ideologies and to protect them from being brainwashed by the CPP-NPA into abandoning their families and studies. The organization is envisioned to enflame the SPIRIT OF VOLUNTEERISM among the youth and student sectors.
R9	Strengthen the civil and political participation of Zambaleño youth through youth governance, youth engagement, youth political education and youth policy.
R10	To serve as the community through various platforms and advocacies.
R11	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To empower the youth 2. To expose them to various local governance programs, projects and activities. 3. To mobilize the youth in promoting various local governance programs, projects and activities. 4. To strengthen volunteerism and rendering of community service among the youth. 5. To have a source of recommendations, suggestions and opinions from the youth sector on community development and social services improvement.

The table revealed that most of the YVOs' objectives affirmed that they imparted the various communities with essential knowledge and developed basic life skills by providing programs and training to build a better community and environment. This is confirmed with the statement of R7, ***"A movement focusing in developing an individual to be a responsive leader in building our nation, and believes that through our collective strength and resources, we can prepare and create an upright environment for next generation."*** It was stated that to help people, one should train them and empower them to have the skills of their own to solve their problems in the future so that they can have a better and efficient community.

Table 2.1 presents the roles of Zambales' YVOs as to leadership.

Table 2.1 Roles of Zambales' YVOs as for Leadership (N=11).

A. Leadership		Weighted Mean	Direct Interpretation
1	It provides training and seminars that focus on disseminating information about the importance of leaders and leadership.	4.27	Excellent
2	It helps in the development of leadership skills through seminars and hands-on activities such as team building.	4.45	Excellent
3	It forms the leadership values that would help the leaders be more efficient and relevant.	4.45	Excellent

4	It provides activities that help improve the qualities of being an excellent leader in serving particular communities.	4.45	Excellent
5	It develops the communicative competence necessary to create good rapport needed to attain the organization's goals.	4.45	Excellent
6	It inspires people to become responsible citizens and help others in their ways, like what the leaders do.	4.91	Excellent
7	It provides effective communication and efficient leadership to transmit information and to coach people, so they must be able to listen to and communicate with a wide range of people across roles and social identities to make a better community.	4.55	Excellent
8	It focuses on improving learning agility wherein a true leader must be able to analyze the given circumstances to know what to do and not to do so that the organization's objective will be achieved in a particular time.	4.45	Excellent
9	To improve the ability to turn failure into success by reflecting constructive criticism to have a better leadership style.	4.73	Excellent
10	It can help develop the relationship of the community through the inculcation of teamwork for the betterment of everyone.	4.91	Excellent
Overall Weighted Mean		4.56	Excellent

As reflected from the table above, it was revealed that indicators 6, "*It inspires people to become responsible citizens and help others in their ways, like what the leaders do*" and 10, "*It can help develop the relationship of the community through the inculcation of teamwork for the betterment of everyone*" were both categorized as *Excellent* with the mean 4.91. This confirmed that people could be good role models or leaders in developing a community by showing the ways on how to do it. When people help others, they can be motivated to help others; then there will be unity, which can lead to the betterment of the community. The idea of leading others to development is the best way to teach them to stand on their own, and eventually, they will be encouraged to be leaders as well. An overall weighted mean of 4.56 is *Excellent* on the roles of YVOs in terms of leadership.

The findings corroborated Dipboye's (2018) assertion that leadership is a process by which a person develops the capacity to influence the behavior and attitude of others. Additionally, Northouse (2016:7) stated that "leadership is the mechanism by which a person influences a group of people to accomplish a common goal." Manteklow (2011) continued by declaring that developing solid relationships becomes critical to success. Kelchner (2013) emphasizes the importance of optimizing diversity within a team to allow individuals with disparate skillsets to collaborate and exchange ideas for the best solution possible. Whetten and Cameron (2011) believed that individuals could develop meaningful relationships that generate energy, significant physiological, mental, intellectual, and social implications follow.

Table 2.2 presents the roles of Zambales' YVOs as to crisis response.

Table 2.2 Roles of Zambales' YVOs as for Crisis Response (N=11).

B. Crisis Response		Weighted Mean	Direct Interpretation
1	It provides relief operation/s to a particular community that experienced calamities.	4.91	Excellent
2	It disseminates information on the ways to survive in times of possible calamities.	4.55	Excellent
3	It enables the affected families to have a better perspective in life by showing them hope and solution in every situation.	4.27	Excellent
4	It helps the affected communities have courage amidst calamities by inspiring them to stand to overcome possible depression.	4.36	Excellent
5	It demonstrates heroism through sharing their valuables and possessions in times of adversity.	4.82	Excellent

6	It possesses the value of unity in times of calamity through fostering love and care for others.	4.82	Excellent
7	It develops the skill in strategic development through providing a quick and effective response to the calamity victims.	4.73	Excellent
8	It enables the calamity victims to reflect on the given situation and help themselves find a way not to have the same situation again and be prepared for the possible calamities in the future.	4.64	Excellent
9	It provides an opportunity for fortunate people to help the affected families provide the basic needs of the calamity victims.	4.64	Excellent
10	It encourages people to characterize " <i>Bayanihan</i> " to help one another, especially in times of need.	5	Excellent
Overall Weighted Mean		4.67	Excellent

As shown in the table above, indicator 10, "*It encourages people to characterize "Bayanihan" to help one another, especially in times of need*" was categorized as **Excellent** with the mean of 5 in terms of Crisis Response. In times of adversity, people can see the heroes, the *Bayanihan* spirit, showing love and care for one another. The idea of helping one another is very common because when people do go things to the needy people, then the people who got the help will help others in need as well in the future. An overall weighted mean of 4.67 is *Excellent* on the roles of YVOs in terms of crisis response.

The findings confirmed the statement of Elmqvist et al. (2019) that YVOs allow communities to plan for a crisis and/or to restore or even transform following a crisis. Additionally, Davarani et al. (2021) stated that a culture of benevolence and benevolence in charity should be institutionalized among the community so that there is a greater force available to provide relief and service to the community during times of crisis.

Table 2.3 presents the roles of Zambales' YVOs as to environmental protection.

Table 2.3 Roles of Zambales' YVOs as to Environmental Protection (N=11).

C. Environment Protection		Weighted Mean	Direct Interpretation
1	It fosters love through environment restoration.	4.73	Excellent
2	It provides seminars and training on how to prevent the destruction of the environment.	4.27	Excellent
3	It enables people to value the environment like how they value themselves.	4.82	Excellent
4	It allows them to realize the importance of the environment in the development of society and, in general, humanity.	4.73	Excellent
5	It provides an opportunity to show gratitude for the things and products that people enjoyed and maximized through activities like hiking, wherein the collected registration fee is used for certain activities related to environmental protection.	4.36	Excellent
6	It allows people to be creative in making reusable materials (old clothes, tarpaulins, plastic bottles, etc.) to be utilized in their new form efficiently.	4.45	Excellent
7	It enables people to join activities such as tree planting to reinforce reforestation in the mountain ranges and such areas.	4.73	Excellent
8	It encourages people to participate in coastal clean-up drives to protect marine life.	5	Excellent
9	It opens partnership with other non-government organizations.	5	Excellent
10	It links partnerships with Government agencies (DENR, LGU).	4.55	Excellent
Overall Weighted Mean		4.66	Excellent

Based on the results, it was confirmed that indicator 8, *“It encourages people to participate in coastal clean-up drives to protect marine life”* and indicator 9, *“It opens partnership with other non-government organizations”* with the mean of 5 that is marked as **Excellent** in terms of environmental protection. With the given circumstances, the destruction of the coastal areas is evident, so many YVOs take part in the preservation through coastal clean-up drives, which are commendable and have a tremendous effect on the coastal areas. Meanwhile, this activity needs coordination with the other organizations that could be of help in the realization of preserving the coastal areas. An overall weighted mean of 4.66 is **Excellent** on the roles of YVOs in terms of environment protection.

The result was supported by Pretty and Frank (2000), who stated that a balance of corporate and government funding had characterized the tradition of long-serving, community-based environmental care organizations. They argue that there must be an adequate current investment in human, social, and natural resources and processes in place to accommodate the changes and restructures common to environmental care organizations.

Table 2.4 presents the roles of Zambales’ YVOs as to Indigenous People.

Table 2.4. Roles of Zambales’ YVOs as to Indigenous People (IP) (N=11).

D. Indigenous People		Weighted Mean	Direct Interpretation
1	It helps to promote IP's products to the target consumers and helps them be knowledgeable and skilful in marketing their products.	4.09	Excellent
2	It conducts community immersions to experience IP's ways of life.	4	Good
3	It encourages IPs to have livelihood programs related to the available resources in their respective localities.	4	Good
4	It allows people to conduct gift-giving/relief operations that would instil sharing values in a community.	4.73	Excellent
5	It helps people appreciate and reflect on cultural differences that make one another meaningful and relevant to society.	4.55	Excellent
6	It provides learning opportunities to impart knowledge and develop essential life skills needed in living their daily lives.	4.45	Excellent
7	It provides information on improving their hygiene through the lecture demonstration and giving of hygiene kits (soaps, toothpaste, toothbrush, and the like).	4	Good
8	It enables them to be educated on how to prevent diseases through the distribution of facemasks, face shields, alcohols, and the likes.	4.18	Excellent
9	It allows them to share each other's interests (playing, dancing, singing, etc.) to build communication.	4.64	Excellent
10	It encourages the IPs to have a better perspective in life by planning their goals and ways to attain them.	4.18	Excellent
Overall Weighted Mean		4.28	Excellent

It was found out that most of the YVOs agreed that indicator 4, *“It allows people to conduct gift-giving/relief operations that would instill sharing values in a community”* ranked first with the mean of 4.73 with an **Excellent** mark. They help the indigenous people by conducting gift-giving or relief operations, depending on the situation. The idea is that when one helps others, it will make them happy and try to help others out of gratefulness and sense fulfillment by sharing what they have. An overall weighted mean of 4.28 shows **Excellent** on the roles of YVOs in terms of indigenous people.

The findings confirmed the statement of Hart and Brossard (2002) that young adults favor service opportunities that include improving the daily lives of the less fortunate in their communities. Many young volunteers express a desire to volunteer in an environment where they can see their efforts making a difference. In a nutshell, they desire up-close and personal volunteer experiences. Additionally, Hustinx and Lammertyn (2003) assert that the motivations for "collective" volunteer activities are rooted in a communal orientation and a deep sense of obligation to one's local society.

Table 2.5 presents the roles of Zambales’ YVOs as to education

Table 2.5 Roles of Zambales' YVOs as to Education (IP) (N=11).

E. Education		Weighted Mean	Direct Interpretation
1	It encourages people to impart their knowledge necessary in the development of the community.	4.45	Excellent
2	It enables individuals to develop the numeracy needed in everyday living.	4.27	Excellent
3	It encourages people to disseminate timely and relevant health issues and entrepreneurship skills that will make the individuals efficient and effective in the community.	3.91	Good
4	It enables people to be educated in the phonemic awareness needed to develop their reading skills and reading comprehension.	4.45	Excellent
5	It helps people be productive by participating in various seminars that enhance their talents and knowledge to create a form of livelihood for their own family.	4.36	Excellent
6	It enables people to donate books that can be utilized as the reference needed in the training and workshop to develop the essential life skills of the attendees.	4.27	Excellent
7	It helps people to recognize the value of individuality by knowing how to socialize with others to achieve common goals in life.	4.64	Excellent
8	It enables people to use their abilities to have better self-confidence necessary to build healthy relationships with people.	4.55	Excellent
9	It enables individuals to improve their skills to have a better life.	4.55	Excellent
10	It encourages people to be self-reliant on every possible occasion.	4.36	Excellent
Overall Weighted Mean		4.38	Excellent

The results revealed that most YVOs confirmed that indicator 7, ***"It helps people recognize the value of individuality by knowing how to socialize with others to achieve common goals in life"*** with the mean of 4.64 marked as ***Excellent*** in terms of Education. They believed that everyone is intelligent in their own ways, as stated by Gardner's Multiple Intelligence. He emphasized that each individual is equally smart when exposed to the development of skills. Communication through socialization is important as it builds healthy and meaningful relationships with others, which is one of the keys to the development of society through proper education. An overall weighted mean of 4.38 is ***Excellent*** on the roles of YVOs in terms of education.

The results confirmed Patterson's (2010, p. 75) statement that a common vision and values thus bind together individuals who collaborate or function in an organic structure. These values represent strongly held personal convictions and serve as a powerful motivator for the community as a whole and a catalyst for cooperation and engagement (Martinelli, 2010 as cited by Sohmen, 2013).

Table 3 presents the best practices of Zambales' YVOs.

Table 3. Best Practices of Zambales' YVOs.

Respondents	Best Practices
R1	Service Above Self
R2	Community Service
R3	Service above self
R4	Bayanihan; to achive the Sustainable Development Goals.
R5	1. Raising awareness to protect, maintain, develop and improve natural resources such as tree planting. 2. Promote "Filipino Bayanihan culture" such as organized outreach programs

R6	Having an operational activity in far flung areas not only for the sake of the environment but also for the sake of all individuals.
R7	1.Coordination with LGU in every activities 2. Cooperation with other organizations 3. Community immersion
R8	Organization’s Advocacy session, Gift giving,Tree Planting,Clean up drive, Feeding, Relief good distribution, Sining Bayanihan, medical mission etc.
R9	Partnered with SK Councils for literacy program, Initiated a donation drive for the typhoon victims, Conducted webinars regarding Youth Participation in Good Governance and Sustainable Development Goals, Partnered with other organizations for Coastal Clean Up Drive
R10	1. Collaboration with other government and non-government organizations in the conduct of various project. 2. Use of connections and linkages through Ayala Group of Companies
R11	1. Information Education Campaign about health 2. Volunteerism on LGU activities 3. Annual Lakbay Alay on IP community

It was revealed that the common best practice of the YVOs is to be selfless by initiating various programs that raise the awareness in protecting the environment and natural resources as well as the promotion of the *Bayanihan* spirit through collaboration with other agencies and linkages to achieve their specific goals, the betterment of the community. As stated by R5, ***“Raising awareness to protect, maintain, develop and improve natural resources such as tree planting”*** and R10, ***“Collaboration with other government and non-government organizations in the conduct of various project. Use of connections and linkages through Ayala Group of Companies. Promote “Filipino Bayanihan culture” such as organized outreach programs.”*** It is indeed vital that each in the community will be selfless and be concerned with each other as much as they value themselves.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

1. Most of the YVOs were situated at Iba, Zambales, the capital of the province. They have access to various government offices that provides many services in the promotion of the common good.
2. Most of the YVOs’ objectives affirmed that they imparted the various communities with essential knowledge and developed basic life skills through providing programs and trainings so each of them will build a better community and environment.

2.1. Roles of Zambales’ YVOs as to Leadership

People can be good role models or leaders in developing a community by showing how to do it. When people help others, they can be motivated to help others; then there will be unity, which can lead to the betterment of the community.

2.2. Roles of Zambales’ YVOs as to Crisis Response

In times of adversity, people can see the heroes, the *Bayanihan* spirit, showing love and care for one another; the idea of helping one another is very common because when people do go things to the needy people, then the people who got the help will help others in need as well in the future.

2.3. Roles of Zambales YVOs as to Environmental Protection

With the given circumstances, at present, the destruction of the coastal areas is evident, so many YVOs take part in the preservation through coastal clean-up drives, which are commendable and have a tremendous effect on the coastal areas.

2.4. Roles of Zambales’ YVOs as to Indigenous People

They help the indigenous people by conducting gift-giving or relief operations, depending on the situation. The idea is that when one helps others, it will make them happy, and they will try to help others out of gratefulness and sense fulfilment by sharing what they have.

2.5. Roles of Zambales’ YVOs as to Education

They believed that everyone is intelligent in their own ways, as stated by Garner’s Multiple Intelligence, wherein he emphasized that each individual is equally smart when they are exposed to the development of skills. Communication through socialization is important as it builds a healthy and meaningful relationship with others which is one of the keys to the development of society through proper education.

3. It was revealed that the common best practice of the YVOs is to be selfless by initiating various programs that raise the awareness in protecting the environment and natural resources as well as the promotion of *Bayanihan* spirit through collaboration with other agencies and linkages to achieve their specific goals, the betterment of community.

RECOMMENDATION

1. It is recommended to have investigated other factors related to the Zambales' YVOs.
2. Further studies may involve more YVOs coming from different provinces in the Philippines.

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